

PHILOSOPHICAL SIGNIFICANCE OF THE NATIONAL IDEA IN THE SPIRITUAL DEVELOPMENT OF YOUTH

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Abstract. This study examines the role of the national idea in ensuring the spiritual maturity of the younger generation, its philosophical content, and its importance in forming a person's worldview. The national idea is analyzed as a spiritual force that forms values such as patriotism, tolerance, humanity, and social responsibility in the hearts of young people. The article also analyzes the educational and philosophical essence of the national idea in strengthening the spiritual immunity of young people in the global information space.

Keywords: Spirituality, national idea, spiritual education, youth, philosophy, values, patriotism, national consciousness, spirituality, ideological immunity.

Introduction

In the current era of globalization, the development of society is determined not only by economic resources, but also by the spiritual level of human capital. In particular, raising the spirituality of young people is the main criterion for the future of the nation and the stability of the state. In this sense, the national idea serves as a philosophical basis that shapes the worldview, value system, and moral orientations of young people. This study analyzes the role of the national idea in the spiritual maturity of the younger generation, its philosophical content, and its significance in strengthening the spiritual immunity of young people in the global information space. The results of the study serve to deepen the pedagogical and philosophical interpretation of the national idea and determine its practical significance in the education of young people. The national idea is a socio-philosophical system formed in the harmony of the historical experience of the people, national values, traditions, cultural heritage and spiritual needs, and constitutes the ideological basis of the development of society. Theoretically, the national idea is manifested as the main factor determining the worldview, spiritual direction and social activity of a person. The concept of the national idea is inextricably linked with the concepts of "social consciousness" and "national identity" in Western philosophy, and serves to strengthen the individual's sense of belonging to his nation, ensure social solidarity and maintain ideological

stability. In Eastern philosophy, the national idea is interpreted as a spiritual criterion of human perfection. From the point of view of pedagogical theory, the national idea is one of the priority areas of education of the younger generation. Because it determines the goals and content of the educational process, directs students to goodness, hard work, humanity and patriotism. Psychologically, the national idea forms the internal motivation of a person, gives impetus to the realization of his identity, the correct assessment of his social role and the development of his will-power qualities. Therefore, the national idea is important not only as an ideological, but also as a psychological factor of personal development.

The national idea is a spiritual concept that unites the historical memory of the people, cultural traditions, social dreams and goals. It is the force that guides human thinking, beliefs, values and life position. From a philosophical point of view, the national idea is a means of understanding the purpose of society's existence, preserving its identity and strengthening faith in the future. The spiritual development of young people is not only education, but also a process of conscious self-awareness. In this process, the national idea appears as a guiding principle for young people, a criterion for evaluating values. Young people instill the national idea through their life experience, cultural environment, family, and education system. Therefore, this idea should be instilled not only through textbooks or slogans, but also as a practical life value.

The national idea teaches young people to consciously choose human values. This protects them from any alien ideologies, consumerist worldview, individualism or moral vacuum. In this sense, the national idea acts as a spiritual "compass" for young people, and a "source of spiritual power" for the nation. Spiritual education is a continuous process that directs a person to moral standards, patriotism and a sense of responsibility. It is carried out through school, family, higher education, the media, art and culture. In this process, the national idea serves as the main ideological and philosophical support. The values of the Uzbek people, formed over the centuries - respect for the elderly, hard work, kindness, family unity - are a practical expression of the national idea. If these values are instilled in the minds of young people during the upbringing process, they will mature into not only educated, but also conscientious, morally pure people. In the global information space, young people are exposed to various ideological trends, cultural influences, advertising and virtual worldviews. In this case, the national idea helps to strengthen their consciousness with moral choice and ideological immunity. Many individualistic, consumerist or hedonistic ideas

are put forward in the modern information flow. If a young person does not think based on national values, he may fall under the influence of such ideas. Consequently, the national idea directs young people to critical thinking, spiritual stability, and social responsibility. Philosophically, the national idea has universal significance: it promotes openness to universal values while preserving nationality. Such an approach educates young people not only as people loyal to their culture, but also as worldview people. The national idea thus forms a person who is integrated into the global world, but who has preserved his “spiritual roots”. In the future, youth spirituality will become even more important as an ideological criterion for the country's development. Therefore, the education system, cultural policy, and the media must operate in harmony with the national idea. The national idea brings young people to a sense of community, “we,” and strengthens their sense of common purpose and interest. This is a philosophical guarantee of social cohesion, peace, and development. It also teaches young people to approach global problems such as appreciating historical heritage, preserving nature, and understanding cultural identity from a national perspective.

Conclusion

Today's youth live in the information age. To strengthen their spiritual immunity, it is necessary to actively promote the national idea in modern forms – digital education, feature films, theater, social networks, and youth forums. Only then can the national idea become not an ancient ideal for young people, but a modern philosophy of life. The importance of the national idea in the spiritual maturity of young people is, first of all, closely related to the process of human self-awareness. From a philosophical point of view, a person turns to his national roots and cultural memory to understand his essence. Therefore, the national idea is not just an ideological concept, but a spiritual phenomenon that returns a person to his historical identity, connecting him with his spiritual source. The realization of identity is a process closely related to the realization of the ideological goals of his nation.

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